

Anomaly-based Intrusion Detection for Zephyr-based Resource-Constrained Devices in IoMT Networks

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Abstract—The integration of the Internet of Things into the healthcare sector has resulted in the emergence of the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) technology. However, IoMT networks remain susceptible to various types of threats due to their heterogeneity and resource-constrained characteristics. Therefore, novel security solutions, such as efficient and accurate Anomaly-based Intrusion Detection Systems (AIDSs), considering the inherent limitations of IoMT networks are required to be developed, before IoMT networks realize their full potential in the market. In our previous work, we focused on developing an AIDS for protecting Linux-based IoMT devices. In this paper, we extend our previous work by presenting the first AIDS specifically designed for resource-constrained IoMT devices using the popular Zephyr RTOS. The implementation details of the proposed AIDS are described, and the runtime performance of the implemented MDA component of the AIDS is evaluated using an nRF52840 Development Kit (DK). The runtime performance evaluation showed a minimized resource consumption (i.e., less than 1% CPU and RAM usage, approximately 1% ROM usage).

Keywords—*anomaly-based intrusion detection, Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), intrusion detection system (IDS), Zephyr RTOS, machine learning algorithms*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, the development of the Internet of Things (IoT) technology has been significant, especially in the healthcare sector. This has resulted in the emergence of the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) technology aiming to improve the patient's quality of life by enabling personalized e-health services without time and location limitations [1]–[3]. However, IoMT networks remain susceptible to different types of threats due to their resource-constrained characteristics and heterogeneity, and this, in turn, means that IoMT networks, as well as the healthcare systems depending

on these networks, face several security and privacy challenges [4]–[6]. Consequently, the development of security solutions protecting IoMT networks from attackers is a necessary step towards ensuring the acceptance and wide adoption of IoMT networks in the coming years.

Nevertheless, conventional security mechanisms remain complex and resource-intensive highlighting their unsuitability for IoMT networks. On the one hand, IoMT networks include resource-constrained IoMT devices with limited processing, storage capacities, and battery lives. On the other hand, the IoMT devices are deployed and interconnected using lightweight communication protocols in a constrained environment that cannot support conventional security mechanisms [7]. Therefore, to ensure that IoMT networks earn the trust of all stakeholders and realize their full potential in the healthcare sector, innovative security mechanisms are crucial to address the pressing security challenges of IoMT networks in an effective and efficient manner taking into account their unique limitations due to resource constraints [8], [9].

In this context, both researchers and industry professionals currently recognize anomaly-based intrusion detection systems (AIDSs) as a promising security solution that can considerably improve the protection of IoT networks as long as novel lightweight AIDSs tailored for resource-constrained environments are developed [7], [10]. Currently, to the best of our knowledge, the literature contains a limited number of AIDSs (i.e., [11]–[16]) regarding the protection of resource-limited IoMT devices within IoMT networks. Among them, only four (i.e., [12], [13], [15], [16]) have been implemented and only our two works among them (i.e., [15], [16]) have been evaluated during runtime. In particular, in our previous work in [16], we presented the system architecture of a novel AIDS specifically designed for resource-constrained Linux-based devices within IoMT networks. The detection process of the proposed AIDS relied on novelty detection and outlier detection algorithms instead of conventional classification algorithms. Moreover, the proposed AIDS was implemented

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for an IoMT device (i.e., Raspberry Pi 4 device) and was evaluated during runtime.

In addition, Zephyr RTOS [17] is a popular Operating System (OS) in IoT [18], [19]. However, our research in the literature showed that there is no AIDS protecting resource-constrained IoMT devices using the Zephyr RTOS. Therefore, in this paper, we extend our previous work in [16] through the presentation of the first AIDS for resource-constrained IoMT devices using the Zephyr RTOS (Real Time Operating System). The runtime performance evaluation results of the implemented MDA component on the resource-constrained Zephyr-based device showed a minimal resource consumption (i.e., 0.8 % CPU usage, 0.19 % RAM usage, 1.07 % ROM usage).

The rest of this work is organized as follows. Section II describes the proposed AIDS for resource-constrained IoMT devices. Then, Section III provides a detailed description of the Monitoring and Data Acquisition (MDA) component of the proposed AIDS, while Section IV presents the Remote Detection Engine (RDE) component of the proposed AIDS. Afterward, Section V includes the runtime performance evaluation of the implemented MDA component. Lastly, Section VI concludes this paper and provides hints for future work.

II. PROPOSED AIDS

As shown in Fig. 1, the proposed AIDS consists of two main components: (a) the monitoring and data acquisition (MDA) component, which is specifically engineered to operate on resource-constrained IoMT devices using the Zephyr RTOS, and (b) the remote detection engine (RDE) component that functions on the gateway.

III. MONITORING AND DATA ACQUISITION COMPONENT

The MDA component is hosted on an IoMT device connected to the gateway. The MDA component performs two operations: (a) it collects data (e.g., CPU usage and memory usage) related to the behavior of the host IoMT device during a specific monitoring period (i.e., the sampling period) and (b) transmits the collected data to the gateway where the RDE component runs. Then, the RDE component on the gateway is

responsible for detecting whether the IoMT device hosting the MDA component has been the target of an attack.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed AIDS in the IoMT network.

In essence, the MDA component runs on an IoMT device that does not possess enough computation resources to perform local intrusion detection on its own. The MDA component is implemented by considering an IoMT device (e.g., nRF52840 Development Kit – nRF52840 DK [20]) running the Zephyr RTOS [17]. The C programming language was used to implement the MDA component since Zephyr RTOS is also implemented in C. In addition, it is worthwhile mentioning that the Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) protocol is used to transmit the collected behavior data to the gateway. The internal architecture of the MDA component, along with its modules, is shown in Fig. 2.

A. Data Collection

The “data collection” module collects behavior data regarding the IoMT device on runtime during a sampling period (i.e., behavior sampling period). Table I presents and describes the sets of features included in the collected behavior data. The output of the “data collection” module is a record in CSV format created based on the collected behavior data.

In particular, the module makes use of the ability of the Zephyr OS to access various statistics (i.e., cpu cycles, memory statistics, heap statistics) through its internal functions (e.g., thread analyzer) and gathers the required

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF FEATURES COLLECTED BY THE “DATA COLLECTION” MODULE OF THE MDA COMPONENT.

Feature name	Index	Descriptions
timestamp	1	Time in milliseconds when the current record was collected.
total_cycles	2	Total number of elapsed cpu cycles that the cpu has been active after system boot.
idle_cycles	3	Number of elapsed cpu cycles that the cpu has been idle after system boot.
threads	4	Number of threads that are active in the cpu at the moment of sampling.
threads_stack_average	5	Percentage of stack used by an active thread in the cpu at the moment of sampling averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_current_cycles_average	6	Number of cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_peak_cycles_average	7	Number of maximum consecutive cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_average_cycles_average	8	Average number of cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
heaps	9	Number of allocated heaps in the system.
alloc_mem_all_heaps	10	Total size of allocated memory of all heaps.
free_mem_all_heaps	11	Total size of free memory of all heaps.
max_alloc_mem_all_heaps	12	Sum of maximum memories that can be allocated for all heaps.

feature values by sampling them once during a sampling period. Table I presents the feature values collected by the “data collection” module along with their descriptions based on the documentation of the Zephyr OS found in [17].

Fig. 2. The Monitoring and Data Acquisition (MDA) component.

At this point, it is important to note that the collected feature values in Table I can be organized into the following three feature groups:

- the “CPU mode” group (i.e., indexes 2–3) containing feature values related to the time (in cycles) that the CPU spends in a specific mode of operation (i.e., active, idle),
- the “thread statistics” group (i.e., indexes 4-8) including feature values that monitor the number of active threads, their stack usage and time spent scheduled in the cpu, and
- the “heap memory” group (i.e., indexes 9–12) including feature values that monitor how the system uses its heap memory.

B. Bluetooth Data Reporter

The “data collection” module sends the collected records to the “bluetooth data reporter” module. For each received collected record, a report is created and transmitted to the gateway by the “bluetooth data reporter” module. The implemented “bluetooth data reporter” module transmits reports to the gateway using the Bluetooth protocol. Two types of information are included in each report: (i) a unique identifier of the device hosting the MDA component, and (ii) the collected record in CSV format. An example of a report is shown below.

MDA report
iomtSensor01
20276,6341,649808,3,0.481,189.667,259.000,164.667,2,224,229652,244

IV. REMOTE DETECTION ENGINE COMPONENT

The RDE component runs on the gateway of the IoMT network and is responsible for three operations:

1. The reception of the MDA reports from the IoMT devices (i.e., hosting the MDA component) that are connected to the gateway,

2. The use of the received MDA reports to identify attack incidents that may have occurred in the connected IoMT devices, and
3. The transmission of appropriate security alerts to the cloud server for further processing and visualization when detecting attack incidents.

The implementation of the RDE component is performed on a gateway device (e.g., Raspberry Pi 4 Model B) running a Debian-based OS (e.g., Ubuntu OS) using the Java programming language and the Python programming language. Moreover, Fig. 3 shows the internal architecture of the RDE component, along with its modules.

Fig. 3. The Remote Detection Engine (RDE) component.

A. Report Receiver

The “report receiver” module is responsible to receive an MDA report during runtime on the gateway from a connected IoMT device hosting the MDA component. After the reception of the MDA report, the “report receiver” module extracts from the report the unique ID of the IoMT device from where the MDA report originates. A check is performed to ensure that the unique ID of the IoMT device is present (i.e., registered) in the configuration file of the RDE configuration. If it is not present, the MDA report is discarded, else the next step happens.

In the next step, either (a) a new CPU thread (i.e., monitoring thread) is created to process the current MDA report or (b) an existing processing thread handles the processing of the current MDA report. Each specific thread created by the “report receiver” module performs intrusion detection for only one specific IoMT device based only on its corresponding received MDA reports. In essence, the intrusion detection for IoMT devices hosting the MDA components is performed separately for each connected IoMT device.

B. Report Verifier

The “report verifier” module processes an MDA report on runtime. It extracts the enclosed record on the MDA report

TABLE II. OUTPUT FEATURE VALUES AFTER THE FIRST PREPROCESSING STAGE.

Feature name	Index	Descriptions
timestamp	1	Elapsed time in milliseconds between the currently collected record and the previously collected record.
total_cycles_delta	2	Total number of elapsed cpu cycles that the cpu has been active since the previously collected record.
idle_cycles_delta	3	Number of elapsed cpu cycles that the cpu has been idle since the previously collected record.
threads	4	Number of threads that are active in the cpu at the moment of sampling.
threads_stack_average	5	Percentage of stack used by an active thread in the cpu at the moment of sampling averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_current_cycles_average	6	Number of cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_peak_cycles_average	7	Number of maximum consecutive cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_average_cycles_average	8	Average number of cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
heaps	9	Number of allocated heaps in the system.
alloc_mem_all_heaps	10	Total size of allocated memory of all heaps.
free_mem_all_heaps	11	Total size of free memory of all heaps.
max_alloc_mem_all_heaps	12	Sum of maximum memories that can be allocated for all heaps.

and performs two checks: (i) the record should follow the CSV format and (ii) the record should contain the expected number of features with their expected types. If the record passes the two checks, it is forwarded to the “data preprocessing” module. Otherwise, the corresponding MDA report is discarded.

C. Data Preprocessor

The “data preprocessing” module receives a record produced by the “report verifier” module as input. The “data preprocessing” module processes the input record in two stages to produce an output preprocessed record in CSV format that can be used by the “detection engine” module.

Based on the description of the features in Table I, it can be observed that some feature values (i.e., features with indexes 1-3) depend heavily on the time that has elapsed since the system boot. The values of these features are continuously increasing as long as the monitored system (i.e., IoMT device) is up and running. In this context, the actual value of these features is not important as much as is the increment that has occurred between subsequent sampling periods. Therefore,

the first pre-processing stage is responsible to decouple the feature values of a collected record from the runtime duration of the underlying system.

In the first preprocessing stage, the feature values with indexes 1–3 are processed, while the remaining feature values are simply forwarded to the second preprocessing stage as these feature values (i.e., indexes 4-12) do not depend on the runtime duration of the system. Table II summarizes the output feature values of a record after the first preprocessing stage.

The second preprocessing stage receives the input of the first preprocessing state and performs normalization on: (a) the feature values of the “CPU mode” feature group, and (b) the feature values of the “heap memory” feature group. The second preprocessing stage is responsible to decouple the feature values of a record produced by the first preprocessing stage from the collection sampling period of the “data collection” module of the MDA component.

In particular, the feature values with indexes 2 and 3 are summed and then each feature value is divided by the

TABLE III. OUTPUT FEATURE VALUES AFTER THE SECOND PREPROCESSING STAGE OF THE “DATA PREPROCESSING” MODULE.

Feature name	Index	Descriptions
total_cycles_perc	1	Percentage of cpu cycles that the cpu has been active during the last sampling period.
idle_cycles_delta	2	Percentage of cpu cycles that the cpu has been idle during the last sampling period.
threads	3	Number of threads that are active in the cpu at the moment of sampling.
threads_stack_average	4	Percentage of stack used by an active thread in the cpu at the moment of sampling averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_current_cycles_average	5	Number of cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_peak_cycles_average	6	Number of maximum consecutive cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
threads_sched_average_cycles_average	7	Average number of cpu cycles that an active thread has been scheduled in the cpu averaged over all active threads.
heaps	8	Number of allocated heaps in the system.
alloc_mem_all_heaps_perc	9	Size of allocated memory of all heaps as a percentage of total heap memory.
free_mem_all_heaps_perc	10	Size of free memory of all heaps as a percentage of total heap memory.
max_alloc_mem_all_heaps	11	Sum of maximum memories that can be allocated for all heaps.

computed sum. This results in a percentage of cpu usage (i.e. percentage of active time vs idle time). Moreover, regarding the features with indexes 10 and 11, their values are summed, and each feature value is then divided by the computed sum. This results in a percentage of heap memory usage (i.e., percentage of allocated heap memory vs free heap memory). In addition, the feature values with indexes 4-9 and 12 are simply forwarded to the output of the second preprocessing stage. Table III summarizes the output feature values of a record after the second preprocessing stage that are also the output of the “data preprocessing” module.

D. Detection Engine

The “detection engine” module receives a preprocessed record from the “data preprocessing” module and identifies potential intrusion incidents targeting the connected IoMT device hosting the MDA component. The output of the “detection engine” module is a detection decision produced using ML algorithms to identify both known and unknown attacks targeting the resource-constrained IoMT devices connected to the gateway. Fig. 4 presents the internal architecture of the “detection engine” module.

Fig. 4. The internal architecture of the “Detection Engine” module of the RDE component.

As shown in Fig. 4, a trained ML model calculates a prediction result for each received preprocessed record (i.e., “1” for abnormal record, “0” for normal record). Subsequently, the calculated prediction result for each record is stored in a FIFO buffer with a length equal to “n”, which is configurable within the RDE component. The FIFO buffer contains the recently calculated prediction result, as well as the previous “n – 1” prediction results that were computed based on the last “n – 1” preprocessed records. Afterward, using all the prediction results inside the FIFO buffer, the average value (i.e., intrusion probability) is calculated and is then compared to a “threshold” value so that the “detection engine” module can determine whether or not an intrusion event has occurred.

In principle, the FIFO buffer ensures that the “detection engine” module considers not only the last received preprocessed record but also a specific number (i.e., n – 1) of previously received preprocessed records for the task of performing intrusion detection. In addition, the length of the FIFO buffer can be configured providing an additional finetuning capability to the intrusion detection process apart from training a better ML algorithm.

Moreover, the “threshold” value that was mentioned is also configurable and its purpose is to provide another manner of fine-tuning the intrusion detection process of the “detection

engine” module. A higher value for the “threshold” parameter signifies that positive decisions (i.e., decisions that an intrusion event has occurred) will occur only at a higher intrusion probability value and vice versa.

Lastly, it is worthwhile mentioning that the “detection engine” module uses custom Python scripts to make a prediction based on one preprocessed record. The functionality of the custom Python scripts follows three steps: (a) parse the input preprocessed record, (b) load the trained ML model, and (c) make a prediction. The use of custom Python scripts facilitates the integration of different ML algorithms into the “detection engine” module of the RDE component.

E. Alert Reporter

The “alert reporter” module receives the detection decisions from the “detection engine” module and transmits an appropriate alert, in JSON format, to the cloud server when an intrusion is detected. The “alert reporter” module can send alerts through either the HTTP application protocol or the MQTT application protocol. Each alert contains three key pieces of information: (i) a timestamp describing when the intrusion incident occurred, (ii) a unique identifier of the device where the MDA component is running, and (iii) the intrusion probability (i.e., decimal number within the range [0, 1]) representing the likelihood that an intrusion incident has occurred. An example of an intrusion alert, in JSON format, produced by the RDE component for a connected resource-constrained device (i.e., “iomtSensor01”), hosting the MDA component, is shown below.

RDE intrusion alert based on detection decision in JSON format

```
{
  "ts": "2024-10-04 10:13:34",
  "dev_ID": "iomtSensor01",
  "intrusion_prob": "1.0"
}
```

V. RUNTIME PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The next step is to train and integrate ML algorithms into the “detection engine” module of the RDE component in order to assess the performance of the implemented AIDS during runtime based on two key aspects: (a) performance evaluation of the ML models in detecting attacks during runtime, and (b) measurement of the computational cost introduced by the MDA component on the resource-constrained IoMT device (i.e., nRF52840 DK).

Regarding the first aspect, we reviewed existing literature to identify suitable datasets ML models. Although several related works [21]–[24] were found, none includes feature values that match or closely resemble those collected by the MDA component of the proposed AIDS. Consequently, these datasets are not suitable for training ML models intended for integration in the proposed AIDS. Generating new datasets tailored to our feature set is necessary but falls outside the scope of this work. Thus, this work is focused on the runtime performance evaluation to measure the resource consumption of the implemented MDA component of the proposed AIDS.

During this evaluation, we used the documentation in [25], [26]. The CPU, RAM and ROM consumption on the

nRF52840 DK with and without the implemented MDA component is shown below in Table IV.

TABLE IV. CPU, RAM, AND ROM CONSUMPTION INTRODUCED BY THE IMPLEMENTED MDA COMPONENT ON THE NRF52840 DK.

Resource	Without MDA	With MDA	MDA usage (difference)
CPU	0.1 %	0.9 %	0.8 %
RAM	12.43 % (32.08 kB)	12.62 % (32.46 kB)	0.19 % (0.38 kB)
ROM	16.08 % (164.59 kB)	17.15 % (175.19 kB)	1.07 % (10.6 kB)

The measurements in Table IV indicate that the implemented MDA component consumes a minimal percentage (i.e., less than 1%) of the available CPU and RAM resources and a small percentage (i.e., approximately 1 %) of the available ROM. Therefore, the implemented MDA component represents a lightweight solution for the proposed AIDS running on resource-constrained IoMT devices whose operating system is the Zephyr RTOS.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented the first AIDS for resource-constrained IoMT devices using the Zephyr RTOS. The implementation details of the proposed AIDS were provided, and the computational overhead introduced by the MDA component on the resource-constrained Zephyr-based device was evaluated. The runtime performance evaluation results showed a minimal resource consumption (i.e., 0.8 % CPU usage, 0.19 % RAM usage, 1.07 % ROM usage).

As future work, we plan to generate new datasets tailored to our feature set for training ML models intended for integration into our proposed AIDS. Towards this direction, we will integrate the nRF52840 DK into the testbed developed in our previous work in [17] and enable data capturing under realistic conditions, facilitating the creation of high-quality datasets. Subsequently, these datasets will be used to train and validate ML models, in terms of their detection accuracy, during runtime.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. J. P. C. Rodrigues *et al.*, “Enabling Technologies for the Internet of Health Things,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 13129–13141, 2018, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2789329.
- [2] M. Papaioannou *et al.*, “A Survey on Security Threats and Countermeasures in Internet of Medical Things (IoMT),” *Trans. Emerg. Telecommun. Technol.*, p. e4049, 2020, doi: 10.1002/ett.4049.
- [3] S. M. R. Islam, D. Kwak, M. H. Kabir, M. Hossain, and K. S. Kwak, “The internet of things for health care: A comprehensive survey,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 3, pp. 678–708, 2015, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2015.2437951.
- [4] P. Gope and T. Hwang, “BSN-Care: A Secure IoT-Based Modern Healthcare System Using Body Sensor Network,” *IEEE Sens. J.*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1368–1376, 2016, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2015.2502401.
- [5] I. Makhdoom, M. Abolhasan, J. Lipman, R. P. Liu, and W. Ni, “Anatomy of Threats to the Internet of Things,” *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 1636–1675, 2019, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2018.2874978.
- [6] A. Tsiota, D. Xenakis, N. Passas, and L. Merakos, “Multi-Tier HetNets With Random DDoS Attacks: Service Probability and User Load Analysis,” *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Secur.*, vol. 20, pp. 6190–6204, 2025, doi: 10.1109/TIFS.2025.3575599.
- [7] I. Essop, J. C. Ribeiro, M. Papaioannou, G. Zachos, G. Mantas, and J. Rodriguez, “Generating datasets for anomaly-based intrusion detection systems in iot and industrial iot networks,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 1–31, 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21041528.
- [8] M. Zhang, A. Raghunathan, and N. K. Jha, “Trustworthiness of medical devices and body area networks,” *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 102, no. 8, pp. 1174–1188, 2014, doi: 10.1109/JPROC.2014.2322103.
- [9] F. Alsubai, A. Abuhusseini, and S. Shiva, “Security and Privacy in the Internet of Medical Things: Taxonomy and Risk Assessment,” in *Proceedings - 2017 IEEE 42nd Conference on Local Computer Networks Workshops, LCN Workshops 2017*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2017, pp. 112–120. doi: 10.1109/LCN.Workshops.2017.72.
- [10] J. Asharf, N. Moustafa, H. Khurshid, E. Debie, W. Haider, and A. Wahab, “A review of intrusion detection systems using machine and deep learning in internet of things: Challenges, solutions and future directions,” *Electronics (Switzerland)*, vol. 9, no. 7. MDPI AG, p. 1177, 2020. doi: 10.3390/electronics9071177.
- [11] G. Thamilarasu, A. Odesile, and A. Hoang, “An intrusion detection system for internet of medical things,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 181560–181576, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3026260.
- [12] A. M. Said, A. Yahyaoui, and T. Abdellatif, “Efficient Anomaly Detection for Smart Hospital IoT Systems,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 4, 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21041026.
- [13] M. Zubair *et al.*, “Secure Bluetooth Communication in Smart Healthcare Systems: A Novel Community Dataset and Intrusion Detection System,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 21, 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22218280.
- [14] U. Zukaib, X. Cui, C. Zheng, M. Hassan, and Z. Shen, “Meta-IDS: Meta-Learning-Based Smart Intrusion Detection System for Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) Network,” *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 11, no. 13, pp. 23080–23095, 2024, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2024.3387294.
- [15] G. Zachos, G. Mantas, K. Porfyraakis, J. de Bastos, and J. Rodriguez, “Anomaly-Based Intrusion Detection for IoMT Networks: Design, Implementation, Dataset Generation, and ML Algorithms Evaluation,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 41994–42028, 2025, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3547572.
- [16] G. Zachos, G. Mantas, K. Porfyraakis, and J. Rodriguez, “Implementing Anomaly-Based Intrusion Detection for Resource-Constrained Devices in IoMT Networks,” *Sensors 2025, Vol. 25, Page 1216*, vol. 25, no. 4, p. 1216, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.3390/S25041216.
- [17] “Zephyr Project Documentation — Zephyr Project Documentation.” <https://docs.zephyrproject.org/latest/index.html> (accessed Jan. 24, 2023).
- [18] S.-I. Hahm *et al.*, “Reliable Real-Time Operating System for IoT Devices,” *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3705–3716, 2021, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2020.3025612.
- [19] M. Farahani, M. A. Rashid, and B. Safaei, “From Kernel to Cloud: A Concise Comparative Study of Practical IoT Operating Systems,” *IEEE Internet Things Mag.*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 92–100, 2025, doi: 10.1109/IOTM.001.2400090.
- [20] “nRF52840 DK - nordicsemi.com.” <https://www.nordicsemi.com/Products/Development-hardware/nRF52840-DK> (accessed Jul. 10, 2025).
- [21] N. Koroniotis, N. Moustafa, E. Sitnikova, and B. Turnbull, “Towards the development of realistic botnet dataset in the Internet of Things for network forensic analytics: Bot-IoT dataset,” *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 100, pp. 779–796, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.FUTURE.2019.05.041.
- [22] A. Alsaedi, N. Moustafa, Z. Tari, A. Mahmood, and A. N. Anwar, “TON-IoT telemetry dataset: A new generation dataset of IoT and IIoT for data-driven intrusion detection systems,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 165130–165150, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3022862.
- [23] M. Ahmed, S. Byreddy, A. Nutakki, L. F. Sikos, and P. Haskell-Dowland, “ECU-IoHT: A dataset for analyzing cyberattacks in Internet of Health Things,” *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 122, p. 102621, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adhoc.2021.102621>.
- [24] J. Areia, I. A. Bispo, L. Santos, and R. L. de C. Costa, “IoMT-TrafficData: Dataset and Tools for Benchmarking Intrusion Detection in Internet of Medical Things,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 115370–115385, 2024, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3437214.
- [25] “CPU load — Zephyr Project Documentation.” https://docs.zephyrproject.org/latest/services/debugging/cpu_load.html (accessed Jul. 10, 2025).
- [26] “Memory report overview.” https://docs.nordicsemi.com/bundle/nrf-connect-vscode/page/guides/memory_overview.html (accessed Jul. 09, 2025).